

THE APPEARANCE OF THE TERM “EDUCATION DICTIONARY” IN WORLD LINGUISTICS IS ANALYZED

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Abstract: *This article discusses the invaluable service of dictionaries in ensuring interlinguistic relations in scientific linguistic literature, researching the grammatical structure of the language, determining language norms, developing the national thinking of society members, the richness of speech, and forming socio-political consciousness. As a result, special dictionaries for learning foreign languages were created in advanced countries of the world.*

Key words: *linguistic literature, interlinguistic relations, lexicography, national thinking, world experience, era of globalization, age of technology.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolda lug‘atlarning ilmiy lingvistik adabiyotlar ichida tillararo munosabatni ta‘minlash, tilning grammatik qurilishini tadqiq qilish, til me‘yorlarini belgilash, jamiyat a‘zolarining milliy tafakkuri, nutq boyligini o‘stirish, ijtimoiy-siyosiy ongni shakllantirishdagi bebaho xizmati haqida fikr boradi. Natijada jahonning ilg‘or davlatlarida xorijiy tillarni o‘rganish uchun maxsus lug‘atlar yaratildi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *lingvistik adabiyotlar, tillararo munosabat, leksikografiya, milliy tafakkur, jahon tajribasi, Globallashuv davri, texnika asri.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается неоценимая заслуга словарей в обеспечении межязыковых связей в научной лингвистической литературе, исследовании грамматического строя языка, определении языковых норм, развитии национального мышления членов общества, богатстве речи, формировании общественно-политического сознания. В результате в передовых странах мира были созданы специальные словари для изучения иностранных языков.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвистическая литература, межязыковые отношения, лексикография, национальное мышление, мировой опыт.*

INTRODUCTION.

The 21st century, which is marked in the history of the world with various names such as the age of high technologies, the age of thinking, the age of general information, the age of globalization, is different from the times that humanity has experienced so far due to the extremely intense

and immeasurable acceleration of the pace of life. In such a situation, if a citizen of every country is loyal to his national values, has a broad worldview, mature mind, can survive various situations with his own intelligence, is independent-minded, strong-willed, and fluent in oral and written speech, different ideological, it is difficult to guarantee that it will withstand the effects of spiritual threats.

The incomparable role of dictionaries in improving the thinking of society is a fact fully justified by world experience and practice. Efforts to develop a person's independent thinking, the ability to correctly and fluently express the product of consciousness, creative thinking, usually begin at a young age. In the last 10 years, the vocabulary has revived somewhat; republishing of political, spiritual, and socially obsolete dictionaries, creating their electronic copies; the vocabulary of our linguistics is rich. However, we cannot say that it has reached the level of developed countries.

Dictionary in English, French, Spanish, German, Russian linguistics has reached a very high level at the moment, especially the network engaged in creating colorful, decorative special educational dictionaries for students of various fields is very advanced. reached

Choosing the material for the dictionary is one of the main problems in creating any dictionary. A distinctive sign of the success of the educational dictionary is that it covers the most necessary and important information, it is clear, short and concise.

MAIN PART. The mass method of selecting material for the dictionary is the criterion of covering the most frequently used words in speech. However, further studies show that when choosing material, it is necessary to choose not only the most frequently used words, but also to not leave out words that are in constant reserve. When analyzing a work of art, it is better to rely on the level of use of words. However, listing the words of a language according to the level of usage is not a very effective method. Because words in the language have different degrees of use in different stylistic environments. In order to improve the criterion of relying on the level of use of words in the selection of material for the educational dictionary, to be covered by other criteria, it is necessary to take into account at least the following three aspects:

1. Relying on the amount and level of use of words.
2. Choosing thematic groups of words.
3. Selection of specialized words related to the type of vocabulary.
4. Preserving the originality of words in translations¹.

It should be mentioned that none of the criteria for collecting words in the dictionary can be the same template for all educational dictionaries, they are modified depending on the topic and purpose of the dictionary.²

One of the main requirements for educational lexicography is to describe all syllables of our lexicon in the necessary forms. The main attention is paid to various semantic, syntagmatic and other aspects of words. Depending on the different aspects of word learning and writing, the following types of learning dictionaries can be created:

1. Dictionaries that determine the rules of correct spelling of words - the educational dictionary of correct spelling of a foreign language.
2. Dictionaries that study the structure and formation system of words - the educational dictionary of foreign language word formation.
3. Dictionaries that determine the level of use of words - a frequency study dictionary of a foreign language.
4. Dictionaries that study the explanation of words, primary and secondary meaning, cognates, cognate forms - educational annotated dictionary of a foreign language.
5. Grammatical dictionaries that study the meaningful parts of words - Vocabulary of a foreign language.
6. Dictionaries that study the historical forms of words - an educational dictionary of obsolete words of the Uzbek language³.

As mentioned above, adverbs are a multifaceted essence and belong to different groups according to their different signs. In word composition analysis, they are indicated by the following conditional symbols: - core;

- word-forming suffix;- lug‘aviy shakl hosil qiluvchi (shakl yasovchi) qo‘shimcha;

^- suffix forming a syntactic form (changing a word);

¹ MR ABDULLAYEVA - development of Russia: Youth look into the future, 2018 NATIONAL COLOR IN LITERARY TRANSLATION (UZBEK LANGUAGE)

² Mengliyev B.M. Bahriddinova B.M., Kholyirov O'. "Textbook of Uzbek language" 2008

³ V.V Morkovkin. Uchebnaya lexicography kak osobaya lingvomethodological discipline. M.: Russian language. 1977, S-28-45

- ◇- complex addition;
- °- formative (homonymous) suffix;
- *- synonymous (synonymous) adverb;
- #- suffix with opposite meaning (antonym);
- ∩- pronunciation (paronym) suffix;

It should be mentioned that most of these dictionaries are being created in electronic form in world linguistics; most of them are waiting for their researchers.

Not only in Uzbek linguistics, but also in world linguistics, dictionaries were originally considered textbooks created for schools, that is, the first examples of dictionaries were actually primitive textbooks created for schools. Later, with the development of vocabulary, their scope expanded.

The complex landscape of today has created a number of problems for education. The sources of information are so diverse and sophisticated that it is difficult to achieve the desired result if the teacher does not convey information in the most convenient, most modern, most interesting and easiest way during the educational process⁴.

CONCLUSION.

It is not easy to attract the student's attention in the age of globalization and technology. Therefore, the field of lexicography has become the most developed field in world linguistics.

Educational dictionaries are designed according to the student's age, interest, and worldview, and can attract his attention, it is a tool for quickly and easily finding the necessary information.⁵

It is also a valuable assistant who can always be with the reader, a resource that enriches the vocabulary, an invaluable treasure that improves the skills of correct writing, correct pronunciation, and word choice. A student can get the help of a dictionary from his parents, teacher and other people, but none of them can be a constant companion of a student with a rich vocabulary.

REFERENCES

⁴ O.Shukurov, B.Boymatova "Synonymous vocabulary of the Uzbek language" 2007-2009.

⁵ Guide for compiling an annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. T.: Science. 1964, -p .84 .

1. Islamov I. Bobojonov SH. "Word grading dictionary of the Uzbek language" 2007-2009.
2. Raxmonkulovna, Abdullayeva Markhabo. "English - uzbek translation process and their analysis." (2021).
3. S.G.Barxudarov, L.A.Novikov. Kakiye doljen bit uchebniy slovar? RYAZR. 1971, №3
4. Abdullaeva MR - ... development of Russia: Young vision and budushchee, 2018 national color and divine translation (Uzbek language)
5. Mengliyev B.M. Bahridinova B.M., Kholiyrov O'. "Textbook of Uzbek language" 2008y.
6. V.V.Morkovkin. Uchebnaya leksikografiya kak osobaya lingvometodologicheskaya dissiplina. M.: Russkiy yazik. 1977, S-28-45
7. Guide to compiling an annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. T.: Science. 1964, 84 p.
8. Абдуллаева, М. (2022). Инглиз – ўзбек бадий таржималарида муқобил вариантни шаклланиш ва ривожланиш босқичлари. Переводоведение: проблемы, решениуа и перспективы, (1), 78-81. https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/translation_studies/article/view/5999
9. O. Shukurov, B. Boymatova "Synonymous vocabulary of the Uzbek language" 2007-2009.
10. Abdullayeva Markhabo et al. "Principles of understanding a positive language in translation (in act of the agata kristi works)." (2020).
11. Ismatullayeva, N. R. (2020). Probability Prediction Strategy In Simultaneous Interpretation. Current research journal of philological sciences, 1(01), 1-6.
12. Khodjaeva, N. (2019). SEMANTICS OF KINSHIP TERMS AS A FORM OF ADDRESS IN UZBEK TRANSLATIONS OF PREMCHAND. Theoretical & Applied Science, (8), 107-110.
13. KHODJAEVA, N. B. (2021). PREMCHAND'S VARDAAN IN UZBEKISTAN: TRANSLATION ISSUES OF SOME CULTURAL SPECIFIC WORDS. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (12), 374-377.
14. KHODJAEVA, N. The Development of Indian Literature in Uzbekistan: Historiography of Translation. History of Translation in India, 431.
15. Ходжаева, Н., & Губаева, Х. (2020). ISSUES ON TRANSLATION OF CHARACTER SPEECH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF KOREAN-UZBEK LITERATURE). МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 3(4).
16. Khodjayeva, N. (2021). The issues of stylistics on translation of historical costumes. ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH, 10(4), 534-543.